

Electrogravity (Unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism)

Occurrence of Unification in the Primordial Atom, In Black Holes, in the Expansion
and in the Center of Matter or Universe

Scientific Article

Area of Study: Physics

Field of Action: Special Relativity, Motion Dynamics, Gravity and Electromagnetism

AUTHOR:

Name: Alberto Mananga Bifica

Academic Data: Meteorologist, graduated from Agostinho Neto University

Contacts: + 244 943687865

Email: albertobifica30@gmail.com / albertobifica.pesquisador@gmail.com

Luanda, December 2019

Summary

Resumen	3
1. Introduction	3
2. Physical interpretation of the time dilation equation	4
3. Unification of Fields.....	5
3.1. Unification of Kinematics with Special Relativity	5
3.2. Unification of Gravity with Special Relativity	5
3.3. Unification of Electromagnetism with Special Relativity.....	6
3.4. Limits conditions for Gravity and Electromagnetism	7
3.5. Expansion of the Universe	7
3.5.1. Primordial Particle or Planck Units.....	8
3.5.2. Current condition of the Universe	9
3.5.3. Universe Expansion Phase.	10
3.6. Black hole.....	11
3.7. Light or Electromagnetic Waves.....	11
3.8. Formulating and Proving The Veracity of Electrogravity Equations Through General Relativity based on Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker Metric Solutions (FLRW) ...	11
3.9. Electrogravity (Unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism)	12
4. Conclusion.....	14
BIBLE REFERENCES.....	15

Resumen

By unifying Gravity with Electromagnetism through Special Relativity, new equations were obtained that explain the entire functioning of these two laws that act in matter or universe through the specific conditions that occur in an expansion ($M = \infty$ e $Q = \infty$), in the center of mass ($R = 0$) and in the continuous process of energy-matter that result in the following equations and in the continuous process of energy-matter that result $v_e = v_g = c^2$, $E_e = E_g = mc^2$ who participate simultaneously in the constant interactions $F_e = F_g = 0$ who is responsible for the expansion and $F_e = F_g = \frac{c^4}{4G}$ who is responsible for the mass. The product $v_e v_g = c^2$ e $F_e F_g = \frac{c^8}{16G^2}$ shows that light is directly caused by the unification of gravity with electromagnetism, that is, this unification is responsible for the wave-particle duality of light.

Keyword: Electromagnetism, Gravity, Light, Unification

1. Introduction

Since the laws of electromagnetic theory began to evolve in the 20th century, the great thinker of the time, Einstein, has tried to unify them with his theory of gravity and turn them into a single force of the Universe. This work aims to contribute to a new understanding of the functioning of gravity and electromagnetism to show under what conditions the two unified forces can be had. His research problem is: Need to unify gravity with electromagnetism; General objective: To find the conditions that allow the unification of gravity with electromagnetism; Specific objective: To unify electromagnetic and gravitational equations through the conditions of the loads, masses and center of matter. As well as finding the general equations of Unification; Hypothesis: If one finds the equations that explain the correct functioning of gravity and electromagnetism, then it will be known under what conditions the two forces become unified

Since the laws of electromagnetic theory began to evolve in the 20th century, the great thinker of the time, Einstein, has tried to unify them with his theory of gravity and turn them into a single force of the Universe. This work aims to contribute to a new understanding of the functioning of gravity and electromagnetism to show under what conditions the two unified forces can be had. His research problem is: Need to unify gravity with electromagnetism; General objective: To find the conditions that allow the unification of gravity with electromagnetism; Specific objective: To unify electromagnetic and gravitational equations through the conditions of the loads, masses and center of matter. As well as finding the general equations of Unification; Hypothesis: If one finds the equations that explain the correct functioning of gravity and electromagnetism, then it will be known under what conditions the two forces become unified.

2. Physical interpretation of the time dilation equation

According to the literature of Special Relativity on time dilation that expresses the times spent by two observers who analyze the same event in different aspects, is represented by the equation:

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1)$$

The equation of time dilation gave the possibility to realize that the faster we move, the time passes slower, that is, if an Earthling travels on his ship near the speed of light for a long time, for him will spend many years in relation to the people who stayed on Earth (Reidel, et al., 1985) (Özer, 2020).

For the study proposed in this article, we will analyze only the cases in which $\Delta t = \Delta t_0$ in agreement with the observers and events as follows:

- If two observers are in a straight line from which light comes from with the same astronomical distances, the light will reach both at the same time or if two photons start from the same source in a straight line at the same instant, so they will have the same distances from their source. Real examples: The light that departs from space reaching for all observers at a coordinate point on Earth; The lamp that is in the center of a sphere that emits light in all directions of the sphere; the propagation of light at the extremes of the expansion of the universe.
- If light photons depart from an end to a particular center or observer, they will have the same times traveled. Real example: Black hole sucking particles of light.

Through the analyses made when $\Delta t = \Delta t_0$ the eq.(1) becomes:

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

Simplifying expressions Δt it's easy to see what's left:

$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = 1 \quad (3)$$

The end result of this simplification shows that $v = 0 \text{ m/s}$ only occurs when observers are paraded in relation to a reference and observe an event in the same perspectives showing that eq.(3) is just a neutral element for $\Delta t = \Delta t_0$ for the cases under review. In the actual examples applied to agreements with the analyses made, observers are points where light is traveling to a certain distance with exhaust velocity, $v = c$, that in relation to black holes corresponds to schwarzschild's radius of event horizon where all matter including light is gravitationally attracted and the same conditions are also valid for

Planck scale which represents a primordial expansion of the Universe in approximately a time of 10^{-43} segundos.

With the analyses made, it is concluded that in the equation of time dilation can act any law of movement or forces according to the relativity of the reference. It is important to note that light was an idea used as a test particle where its velocity made the relative moment between two observers. In this case, Ainstein could use another test particle with high or less speeds than light. Therefore, instead of standardizing light c in the equation of the time dictation, this could vary according to the speed of any particle that would make the relative moment, represented by the symbol $\mathcal{E}$. In this case the equation could be written as follows: $\Delta t = \frac{\Delta t_0}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{\mathcal{E}^2}}}$ where

Ainstein considered $\mathcal{E} = c$.

3. Unification of Fields.

3.1. Unification of Kinematics with Special Relativity

Knowing that $R = \frac{1}{2}a\Delta t^2$ (Halliday, et al., 2014), is obtained for the events(Halliday, et al., 2014), is obtained for the events, $\Delta t = \Delta t_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2R}{a}}$, that then replacing them in the eq.(1) you get

$\sqrt{\frac{2R}{a}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2R}{a}}}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$; subsequently, the roots, components of $2R$ and cross system applies to obtain $a\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = a$. By the equation of acceleration, $a = \frac{v^2}{2R}$, replaced in the right member becomes replaced in the right member becomes $a\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = \frac{v^2}{2R}$; then transports and factorizes the speeds on the left to obtain then transports and factorizes the speeds on the left to obtain $v^2\left(\frac{1}{2R} + \frac{a}{c^2}\right) = a$; using the common denominator rule for the components using the common denominator rule for the components $2R, c^2$ and then isolating v^2 , finally, you get:

$$v^2 = \frac{2aRc^2}{c^2+2aR} \quad (4)$$

3.2. Unification of Gravity with Special Relativity

The equations $v = \frac{2GM}{R}$ e $a = \frac{GM}{R^2}$ (Halliday, et al., 2014; Abbott, et al,1999) are replaced in the eq.(4) to get:

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{c^2}{Rc^2+2GM} \quad (5)$$

It is obtained, respectively, through the eq.(5) the following formulas:

• **Gravitational Escape Speed:** Replaces eq.(5) in the equation $v_g^2 = \frac{2GM}{R}$ to getr:

$$v_g^2 = \frac{2GMc^2}{Rc^2+2GM} \quad (6)$$

- **Gravitational Acceleration for Any Body:** Replaces eq.(5) in the equation $a_{gc} = \frac{GM}{R^2}$ to get:

$$a_{gc} = \frac{GMc^4}{(Rc^2+2GM)^2} \quad (7)$$

- **Gravitational Acceleration to Black Holes Attracting Light or Light Attracting Matter:**

Replaces eq.(5) in the equation $a_{gb} = \frac{c^2}{2R}$ to get:

$$a_{gb} = \frac{c^4}{2(Rc^2+2GM)} \quad (8)$$

- **Gravitational Energy:** In view of the $E_g = mv_g^2$, therefore, you get:

$$E_g = \frac{2GMmc^2}{Rc^2+2GM} \quad (9)$$

3.3. Unification of Electromagnetism with Special Relativity.

The Equations $v = \frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon mR}$ e $a = \frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon mR^2}$ are replaced in the eq.(4) to get:

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{2\pi\epsilon mc^2}{2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2} \quad (10)$$

It is obtained, respectively, through the eq.(10) the following formulas:

- **Electromagnetic Escape Speed:** The eq.(10) is replaced in the equation $v_e^2 = \frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon mR}$ to get:

$$v_e^2 = \frac{Zq^2 c^2}{2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2} \quad (11)$$

- **Electromagnetic Acceleration for Any Body:** The eq.(10) is replaced in the equation

$a_{ec} = \frac{ZqQ}{4\pi\epsilon mR^2}$ to get:

$$a_{ec} = \frac{\pi\epsilon mZq^2 c^4}{(2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2)^2} \quad (12)$$

- **Electromagnetic Acceleration for Black Holes Attracting Light or Light Attracting**

Matter: The eq.(10) is replaced in the equation $a_{eb} = \frac{c^2}{2R}$ to get:

$$a_{eb} = \frac{\pi\epsilon mc^4}{2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2} \quad (13)$$

- **Energia Eletromagnética:** It is known that $E_e = mv_e^2$, so you get:

$$E_e = \frac{Zq^2 mc^2}{2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2} \quad (14)$$

3.4. Limits conditions for Gravity and Electromagnetism

Comparison of Newton's gravitational equations and proposed by the results of this article.

Data: $c = 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$, $G = 6,67 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Nm}^2 \text{ Kg}^{-2}$, $R_{Earth} = 6,371 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}$ e $M_{Earth} = 5,972 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ Kg}$ replacing them in the equations you get:

$$v_g = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{R}} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot 6,67 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 5,972 \cdot 10^{24}}{6,371 \cdot 10^6}} = 11185.83 \text{ m/s}$$

$$v_g = \sqrt{\frac{2GMc^2}{Rc^2 + 2GM}} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot 6,67 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 5,972 \cdot 10^{24} \cdot 3 \cdot 10^8}{6,371 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 3 \cdot 10^8 + 2 \cdot 6,67 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 5,972 \cdot 10^{24}}} = 11185.83 \text{ m/s}$$

An equality in the values of velocities is also noted, the same also results for comparison of other quantities involving gravity and electromagnetism.

Gravitational equations vary in the ranges of $0 \leq M \leq \infty$ e $0 \leq R \leq \infty$. Electromagnetic equations vary in the range of $0 \leq m \leq \infty$, $0 \leq q \leq \infty$ e $0 \leq R \leq \infty$. For instance:

- If $M = \infty$ you get in the formula: $v_g = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{\frac{2GMc^2}{Rc^2 + 2GM}} = \sqrt{\frac{2G \cdot \infty \cdot c^2}{Rc^2 + 2G \cdot \infty}} = \frac{\infty}{\infty}$, raising indetermination results in $v_g = c$, therefore, this implies saying that matter expands to infinity with the speed of light.
- If $R = 0$ you get in the formula: $v_g = \lim_{R \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{\frac{2GMc^2}{Rc^2 + 2GM}} = \sqrt{\frac{2GMc^2}{0 \cdot c^2 + 2GM}}$, results in $v_g = c$, therefore, this implies saying that at the center of any matter the gravitational escape velocity reaches the value of the light velocity.

As mentioned, through the M, m, q and R conditions that are limited to $[0, \infty[$ are introduced into their respective gravitational and electromagnetic equations for the detailed study of matter or Universe according to each specific case.

3.5. Expansion of the Universe

The expansion of the Universe always involves the action of forces due to the presence of energy, matter and light, so the study of its time, its hubble constant and other physical quantities involved in this process, must be done with uniformly varied rectilinear movement.

The density of the expansion can be calculated by the law of gravity, $v_g^2 = \frac{2GM}{R} = H^2 R^2$ where $M = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 d_c$, finally, you get:

$$d_c = \frac{3H^2}{8\pi G} \quad (15)$$

If gravity is valid for determining the critical density of the Universe (d_c), then its mass, radius, expansion time are also calculated by the same law. To obtain the expansion time is

made. $v_g^2 = \frac{2GM}{R}$ and knowing that $R = \frac{1}{2}vt$, this implies that $v = \frac{2R}{t}$ the equation becomes:
 $\frac{4R^2}{t^2} = \frac{2GM}{R} \rightarrow \frac{4R^2}{t^2} = \frac{2G}{R} \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 d_c$, finally, you get:

$$t = \frac{2R}{v} = \frac{2}{H} \quad (16)$$

One of the important conditions of the new equations for the expansion of the Universe are:

- If $M = \infty$ obtained in the formulas: $v_g = c$, $E_g = Mc^2$ e $a_{gc} = a_{gb} = 0$; if $Q = \infty$ obtained in the formulas: $v_e = c$, $E_e = mc^2$ e $a_{ec} = a_{eb} = 0$. These results show that mass and load that tend to infinity expand and make $v_e = v_g = c$, $E_e = E_g = Mc^2$ and it can be said that $F_e = F_g = 0$ which is the force responsible for the expansion of matter or Universe.
- If $R = 0$ obtained in the formulas: $v_g = c$, $E_g = mc^2$ e $a_{gc} = a_{gb} = \frac{c^4}{4GM}$; $v_e = c$, $E_e = mc^2$, $a_{ec} = a_{eb} = \frac{\pi\epsilon m c^4}{Zq^2}$ and for $F_e = ma_e$, finally, one can formulate $F_{ec} = F_{eb} = \frac{\pi\epsilon m^2 c^4}{Zq^2}$. If $a_{gc} = a_{gb} = \frac{c^4}{4GM}$, therefore, it is also valid for formula already known $a_{gc} = a_{gb} = \frac{GM}{R^2}$, when comparing $\frac{GM}{R^2} = \frac{c^4}{4GM}$ and passing the mass M of the right limb to the left, finally gets $F_{gc} = F_{gb} = \frac{GM^2}{R^2} = \frac{c^4}{4G}$. How $v_e = v_g = c$ is also valid $a_e = a_g$ that becomes $\frac{\pi\epsilon m c^4}{Zq^2} = \frac{c^4}{4GM}$ and $F_e = F_g$ that becomes $\frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon R^2} = \frac{GM^2}{R^2}$ or $\frac{\pi\epsilon m^2 c^4}{Zq^2} = \frac{c^4}{4G}$, that is, $F_e = F_g = \frac{c^4}{4G}$ which is the force responsible for matter or Universe in relation to its center depending on the mass or load

It is noted that every process of expansion from the primordial particle to the current phase, the Universe interacted with itself or with light. Through the two conditions mentioned taking into account $t = 0$ and for each $t = \infty$ the exhaust speeds for a given system under study makes it:
 $c^2 = 2aR = \frac{2GM}{R} = \frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon m R} = \left(\frac{Zq^2}{\epsilon nh}\right)^2$. These results allow to obtain an equivalent equation of unification that relates mass and load:

$$4\pi G m^2 = \frac{Zq^2}{\epsilon} = nhc \text{ ou } 4\pi G m M = \frac{ZqQ}{\epsilon} = nhc \quad (17)$$

3.5.1. Primordial Particle or Planck Units.

For planck units or primordial atom expansion conditions already rectified, where h_p is planck's constant and ϵ is the electrical permissiveness of the vacuum, so through the eq.(17) you get:

- **Primordial Particle Charge:**

$$q_p = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon n h_p c}{Z}} = 1,3263 \cdot 10^{-18} C \quad (18)$$

- **Primordial Particle Mass:**

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{nh_p c}{4\pi G}} = 1,5402 \cdot 10^{-8} k_g \quad (19)$$

• **Length or Radius of the Primordial Particle:** Knowing that $l_p = \frac{2Gm_p}{c^2}$ becomes:

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{Gnh_p}{\pi c^3}} = 2,2824 \cdot 10^{-35} m \quad (20)$$

• **Primordial Particle Time:** Using Equation $R = \frac{1}{2} vt$ taking into account planck's units becomes. $l_p = \frac{1}{2} ct_p$ to get:

$$t_p = \sqrt{\frac{4Gnh_p}{\pi c^5}} = 1,5216 \cdot 10^{-43} s \quad (21)$$

• **Primordial Particle Hubble Constant:** Using eq.(16) you get:

$$H_p = \frac{c}{l_p} = \frac{2}{t_p} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi c^5}{Gnh_p}} = 1,3144 \cdot 10^{43} s^{-1} \quad (22)$$

• **Primordial Particle Critical Density:** Replacing eq.(22) in eq.(15) you get:

$$d_p = \frac{3H_p^2}{8\pi G} = 3,0924 \cdot 10^{95} Kg \cdot m^{-3} \quad (23)$$

• **Primordial Particle Energy:**

$$E_p = m_p c^2 = 4,6206 J \quad (24)$$

• **Primordial Particle Strength:**

$$F_p = \frac{Gm_p^2}{l_p^2} = \frac{Zq_p^2}{4\pi\epsilon l_p^2} = m_p \frac{c^2}{2l_p} = \frac{c^4}{4G} = 3,0366 \cdot 10^{43} N \quad (25)$$

3.5.2. Current condition of the Universe

A current condition of the Universe depends on the expansion through the Hubble constant ($H_o = 2 \cdot 10^{-18} s^{-1}$) where mass and load can be calculated respectively by gravitational and electromagnetic laws. Como $v_g^2 = \frac{2GM}{R_u} = H_o^2 R_u^2$, knowing that light reaches the extremes of the Universe, immediately, the speed of expansion is $v_g = c$, this implies that $c^2 = \frac{2GM_u}{R_u} = H_o R_u$ to obtain:

• **Universe Expansion Radius:**

$$R_u = \frac{c}{H_o} = 1,304 \cdot 10^{26} m \quad (26)$$

• **Mass of Universe Expansion:**

$$M_u = \frac{c^3}{2GH_0} = 8,8018. 10^{52} Kg \quad (27)$$

• **Charge of Universe Expansion:** By eq.(17) relationships are valid $4\pi\epsilon Gm_p M_u = Zq_p Q_u$ or $4\pi\epsilon GM_u^2 = ZQ_u^2$ to get:

$$Q_u = \frac{c^3}{H_0} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\epsilon}{ZG}} = 7,5797. 10^{42} C \quad (28)$$

• **Critical Density of the Universe:** By eq.(15) you get:

$$d_u = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G} = 1,4033. 10^{-26} Kg. m^{-3} \quad (29)$$

• **Time of Universe Expansion:** By eq.(16) you get:

$$t_u = \frac{2}{H_0} = 8,6957. 10^{17} s = 2,7574. 10^{10} years = 28 \text{ billions of years} \quad (30)$$

• **Planck's Variation for Universe Expansion:**

The Planck constant is not compatible with the mass and load values of the Universe in the eq.(17), this immediately shows that you must have in the equation a variation of Planck (h_u) depending on the expansion time becoming $4\pi GM^2 = \frac{ZQ^2}{\epsilon} = nh_u c$. To validate and make the equation operational, the equation is $h_u = \frac{4\pi GM^2}{nc} = \frac{ZQ^2}{\epsilon nc} = \frac{\pi c^5}{nGH^2}$ to get:

$$h_u = \frac{\pi c^5}{nGH_0^2} = 2,1865. 10^{88} J. s \quad (31)$$

• **Energy of The Expansion of the Universe:**

$$E_u = M_u c^2 = 2,6405. 10^{61} J \quad (32)$$

• **Force of Universe Expansion:**

$$F_u = \frac{GM_u^2}{R_u^2} = \frac{ZQ_u^2}{4\pi\epsilon R_u^2} = M_u \frac{c^2}{2R_u} = \frac{c^4}{4G} = 3,0366. 10^{43} N \quad (33)$$

3.5.3. Universe Expansion Phase.

Since there is a constant force that controls or acts in the matter of expansion from the primordial atom to the current state, but with different times ranging from t_p à t_u , therefore, an equation is created that goes beyond the established limits and can review the regressive state before the big bang and predict the progressive state of the expansion that allows to calculate the mass variations. (M_v), charge (Q_v) and planck variation. (h_v) depending on the variation of time:

$$M_v = \frac{c^3}{4G} t_v; Q_v^2 = \frac{\pi \epsilon c^6}{4ZG} t_v^2; h_v = \frac{\pi c^5}{4nG} t_v^2 \text{ e } R_v = \frac{1}{2} c t_v \quad (34)$$

3.6. Black hole

If $M = 0$ obtained in the formulas: $v_g = 0, E_g = 0, a_{gc} = 0$ e $a_{gb} = \frac{c^4}{2R}$; If $q = 0$ obtained in the formulas: $v_e = 0; E_e = 0, a_{ec} = 0$ e $a_{eb} = \frac{c^2}{2R}$. These results show the behavior of a particle without mass and charge where the only actuating acceleration is from the black hole ($a_{eb} = a_{gb} = \frac{c^2}{2R}$); the condition $R = 0$ is also applied to black holes. When comparing $\frac{c^2}{2R} = \frac{c^4}{4GM}$ ou $\frac{c^2}{2R} = \frac{GM}{R^2}$, finally, you get $F_e = F_g = \frac{c^4}{4G}$ which is responsible for attracting particles and in this process the speed of light becomes null or loses its movement. Based on the statements one can obtain the Schwarzschild radius which is the event horizon zone:

$$R = \frac{2GM}{c^2} \quad (35)$$

3.7. Light or Electromagnetic Waves

The condition that proves that light is an electromagnetic wave is $m=0$ which results in equations: $v_e = c, E_e = 0, a_{ec} = 0$ e $a_{eb} = 0$. The result shows that particles without mass with undulating behavior do not interact with any matter.

The results of this chapter state that gravitational and electromagnetic forces become a unified constant ($F_e = F_g = \frac{c^4}{4G} = 3,0366 \cdot 10^{43} \text{ N}$) at the center of any matter as a function of its mass or charge, in the primordial atom, in black holes and in the expansion of matter or Universe.

3.8. Formulating and Proving The Veracity of Electrogravity Equations Through General Relativity based on Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker Metric Solutions (FLRW)

The Approaches made in chapters 2 to 3.6 explain in detail the conditions and zones of the Universe that allow the unification of fields between gravity and electromagnetism, without using mathematical concepts such as derivatives, integrals or metrics, using only more traditional methods such as substitutions and artifices. These same equations obtained earlier can also be found in the final result of the metric (FLRW).

The final equation of the FLRW metric is formulated by:

$$\frac{\dot{a}(t)^2}{a(t)^2 c^2} + \frac{K}{a(t)^2} - \frac{\Lambda}{3} = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2} \rho \quad (36)$$

Recital $\dot{a}(t) \equiv v, a \equiv R$, cosmological constant, $\Lambda = \frac{3H_0^2}{c^2}$ e $K = 1$ becomes:

$$\frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{1}{R^2} - \frac{H_0^2}{c^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2} \rho \quad (37)$$

It is known that $v = H_o R$ e $\rho = \frac{3H_o^2}{8\pi G}$ becomes $\frac{H_o^2 R^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{1}{R^2} - \frac{H_o^2}{c^2} = \frac{H_o^2}{c^2}$ by simplifying and isolating c , an equation is obtained that proves that light is the speed of the expansion of the Universe:

$$c = H_o R$$

Immediately, it is possible to notice that $v = c$, $\frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{H_o^2}{c^2}$ ou $\frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{H_o^2}{v^2}$, therefore, the eq.(37), can become:

$$\rho = \frac{3H_o^2}{8\pi G}$$

Through $\rho = \frac{M}{V}$ e $v = H_o R$ replaced in the eq.(37) becomes $\frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{8\pi G M}{3c^2 V}$. Como $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3$ and by isolating R , a result is obtained through this article that shows that the solutions of the FLRW metric are also explained to black holes.

$$R = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$$

When considering. $\Lambda \equiv 0$ e $\rho = \frac{3H_o^2}{8\pi G}$ the FLRW equation becomes $\frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{H_o^2}{c^2}$. How $H_o = \frac{v}{R}$ you get $\frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2}$. It is considered $\frac{1}{c^2} = \frac{R}{2GM}$ of the right member to obtain $\frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{v^2}{2GMR}$. It is considered $\frac{1}{R^2} = \frac{a}{GM}$ of the second expression of the left limb to obtain $\frac{v^2}{R^2 c^2} + \frac{a}{GM} = \frac{v^2}{2GMR}$. Recital $v = 2aR$ and simplifying the accelerations of both members, therefore, we get:

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{c^2}{Rc^2 + 2GM}$$

Through one of the fundamental equations of electrogravity, $4\pi\epsilon GmM = Zq^2$ Isolating $2GM = \frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon m}$, therefore, you get:

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{2\pi\epsilon mc^2}{Zq^2 + 2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R}$$

Based on these demonstrations, the equations of electrogravity are valid and approved according to the equations of General Relativity.

3.9. Electrogravity (Unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism)

Through these arguments already explained, key equations of field unification will be found, that is, electrogravity. Knowing that $F_e = F_g$, this implies that $\frac{\pi\epsilon Zq^2 m^2 c^4}{(2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2)^2} = \frac{GMm c^4}{(Rc^2 + 2GM)^2}$, simplifying you get $\frac{GM}{(Rc^2 + 2GM)^2} = \frac{\pi\epsilon m Zq^2}{(2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2)^2}$. To facilitate the calculation process, the following: $GM = a$; $Zq^2 = b$; $Rc^2 = c$ e $\pi\epsilon m = d$ to get:

$\frac{a}{(c+2a)^2} = \frac{db}{(2dc+b)^2} \rightarrow 4ad^2c^2 + ab^2 = bdc^2 + 4dba^2$ by grouping the similar terms and factoring the equation, the following results are obtained: I) $4ad(dc^2 - ab) = b(dc^2 - ab)$ e II) $dc^2(4ad - b) = ab(4ad - b)$ and the equation system becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \text{I) } 4ad = b \\ \text{II) } ab = dc^2 \end{cases} \text{ using substitution rules in the equation system, you also get } \begin{cases} \text{III) } b = 2dc \\ \text{IV) } 2a = c \end{cases},$$

soon, returning the expressions, you get:

$$\begin{cases} \text{I) } 4ad = b \rightarrow 4\pi\epsilon GmM = Zq^2 \\ \text{II) } ab = dc^2 \rightarrow GMZq^2 = \pi\epsilon mR^2c^4 \end{cases} \text{ e } \begin{cases} \text{III) } b = 2dc \rightarrow Zq^2 = 2\pi\epsilon mRc^2 \\ \text{IV) } 2a = c \rightarrow 2GM = Rc^2 \end{cases}$$

Through the equation $GMZq^2 = \pi\epsilon mR^2c^4$ you get:

$$\frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon mR} \frac{2GM}{R} = c^4 \rightarrow v_e v_g = c^2 \quad (38)$$

By the formulas obtained in this article, the electrogravitational velocity, $v_{eg}^2 = v_e v_g = c^2$, becomes:

$$v_{eg}^2 = \sqrt{\left(\frac{zq^2c^2}{2\pi\epsilon mc^2R + Zq^2}\right) \left(\frac{2GMc^2}{Rc^2 + 2GM}\right)} \quad (39)$$

The equations (38) e (39) prove that the product v_e and v_g is an elementary unit equal to the speed of light, so light is a direct action caused simultaneously by the unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism, that is, light or any matter with. $v = c$ is the means that allows the unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism.

To obtain the equation of the electromagnetic energy, it multiplies eq.(38) by the expression $\frac{m}{m}$ to become $\frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon mR} \frac{2GM}{R} \frac{m}{m} = c^4$ and finally you get:

$$\frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon R} \frac{2GMm}{R} = m^2c^4 = E_{eg}^2 \rightarrow E_e E_g = E_{eg}^2 \quad (40)$$

By equation $\frac{Zq^2}{2\pi\epsilon R} \frac{2GMm}{R} = E_{eg}^2$ multiplied by the expression $\frac{4R^2}{4R^2}$ then you get:

$$4R^2 \frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon R^2} \frac{GMm}{R^2} = E_{eg}^2 \rightarrow 4R^2 F_e F_g = E_{eg}^2 \quad (41)$$

It is known that $F = m \frac{v^2}{2R}$, so you can write $E_{eg} = 2F_{eg}R = mc^2$ replaced in eq.(41) becomes:

$4R^2 F_e F_g = (2F_{eg}R)^2$ finally, you get an equation of the electrogravitational force:

$$F_e F_g = F_{eg}^2 \quad (42)$$

Under the conditions under which $F_e = F_g$ it is also inferred that $F_{eg} = F_e = F_g$, therefore, the eq.(42) becomes $F_e F_g = \frac{c^8}{16G^2}$. It is known that $F_g = \frac{GMm}{R^2}$ and $F_e = \frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon R^2}$ the eq.(42) can also become:

$$\frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon R^2} \frac{GMm}{R^2} = F_{eg}^2 \quad (43)$$

The eq.(42) e eq.(43) prove that electrogravity is the simultaneous interaction between masses and loads, that is, the product between F_e and F_g which occurs under the conditions already mentioned when $v = c$ showing that $a_e = a_g = \frac{c^2}{2R}$. Thus, gravitational and electromagnetic interactions occur simultaneously through matter, so you get: $m \frac{c^2}{2R} M \frac{c^2}{2R} = F_{eg}^2$ where m represents the mass responsible for the charge. (q) to get:

$$F_{eg}^2 = c^4 \frac{mM}{4R^2} \quad (44)$$

By the obtained formulas, the electrogravitational force, $F_{eg} = \frac{c^4}{4G}$ ou $F_{eg}^2 = F_e F_g$ obtain respectively:

$$F_{eg} = \frac{zq^2 c^2}{2(2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2)} \frac{Mc^2}{(Rc^2 + 2GM)} \quad (45)$$

$$F_{eg}^2 = \frac{\pi\epsilon m^2 Zq^2 c^4}{(2\pi\epsilon mc^2 R + Zq^2)^2} \frac{GMmc^4}{(Rc^2 + 2GM)^2} \quad (46)$$

The equations (45) e (46) their maximum interactions always result in $F_{eg} = \frac{c^4}{4G}$ which illustrates in a simple way the force responsible for the unification of Gravity with Electromagnetism, that is, the closer the matter approaches the speed of light it tends to expand to infinity and also the possibility of wave-particle duality act by means of electrogravitational force.

4. Conclusion

The results showed that both gravity and electromagnetism become equal when interactions reach their highest speed value equal to light. This equality occurs at the center of matter as a function of its mass or charge, in the Primordial Atom, in the black holes and in the process of the expansion of the m Universe. In this way it has been proven that these two laws are actually one, through the equations $F_e F_g = \frac{c^8}{16G^2}$ and $v_e v_g = c^2$ showing that every secret of this unification is in the very light that has the behavior of wave-particle duality, which when it is in an intense field of interaction suffers attraction of the system. The same equations with their respective conditions illustrated $F_e = F_g = 0$ who is responsible for the expansion and $F_e = F_g = \frac{c^4}{4G} = 3,0366 \cdot 10^{43} N$ who is responsible for the matter of the Universe.

BIBLE REFERENCES

1. A. Einstein, *Annalen Phys.* **35**, 898 (1911).
2. A. Einstein, B. Podolsky, and N. Rosen, *Phys. Rev.* **47**, 777 (1935).
3. DOES, W.; **Gravity Travel at the Speed of Light?** UCR Mathematics. 1998. Revisa do em 3 July 2008
4. Halliday, Resnick. *Fundamentals of Physics: Volume 1 and 2 Mechanics and Electromagnetism.* 10.ed. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2014. 1450p. available in: <https://salmanisaleh.files.wordpress.com/2019/02/fundamentals-of-physics-textbook.pdf>. Viewed in: 20/07/2021.
5. Halliday, Resnick, Walker, Jearl. *Fundamentals of Physics: Volume 4 Optics and Modern Physics.* 8.ed. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2009. 438p
6. Halliday, Resnick, Robert. *Fundamentals of Physics: Electromagnetism.* 9. ed. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2013.
7. J. Levy, Aether theory and the principle of relativity, in *Ether Space-Time and Cosmology Volume 1*, Michael C. Duffy and Joseph Levy Editors (PD Publications Liverpool UK, March 2008) p 125-138. Arxiv: physics/0607067
8. J. Maldacena and L. Susskind, *Fortsch. Phys.* **61**, 781 (2013). [arXiv:1306.0533 [hep-th]].
9. J.J. Sakurai e Jim Napolitano, *Modern Quantum Mechanics* (Addison-Wesley, Boston, 2011), 2nd edition.
10. Norton, John D. Reports on progress in physics 56, no. 7: 791. (1993); Norton, John D." Einstein, Nordstrom, and the Early Demise of Scalar, Lorentz Covariant Theories of Gravitation." *The genesis of general relativity.* Springer, Dordrecht, 2007. 1337-1411.
11. MEIRA FILHO, D. P.; KAMASSURY, J. K. S.; MEIRA, R. C. S. Uma discussão sobre o coeficiente de restituição. *Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física*, v. 39, n. 4, p. 1-11, 2017.
12. MOURÃO, R. R. F. *Da Terra às Galáxias: Uma Introdução à Astrofísica.* 3. ed. Petrópolis: Editora Vozes Ltda, 1984.
13. M. Lachieze-Rey, *Astron. Astrophys.* **376**, 17 (2001). [gr-qc/0107010].
14. M. Özer, "Electrostatic time dilation and redshift", *Phys. Lett. B*, 802, 135212 (2020).
15. M. Özer, "On the Equivalence Principle and a Unified Description of Gravitation and Electromagnetism", arXiv:gr-qc/9910062v5 (2000).
16. M.P. Hobson, G. Efstathiou, A.N. Lasenby, "General Relativity - an introduction for physicists", Cambridge University Press, pp. 516 (2006)
17. P.W. Bridgman, "Reflections of a Physicist", *Philosophical Library, Inc.*, New York, pp. 333, 334 (1955).
18. P. Abbott, et al., "Observation of gravitational waves from a binary black hole merger", *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 116 061102 (2016).
19. SEIXAS, W. O Princípio da Relatividade - de Galileu a Einstein. *Revista Brasileira de História da Matemática*, v. 5, p. 43–56, 2005.

20. SOUZA, R. E. Introdução á Cosmologia. São Paulo: Editora da Universidade de São Paulo, 2004.
21. S. Baessler et al., "Improved Test of the Equivalence Principle for Gravitational Self-Energy", Phys. Rev. Lett. 83 3585 (1999).
22. J. Levy, Two-way speed of light and Lorentz-Fitzgerald's contraction in aether theory, ArXiv: physics/0603267.
23. Reidel, et al., The Logic of special relativity (Cambridge University press, 1967). Light in Einstein's Universe (1985).